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Specification of output from the IDT Preprocessing and Location Estimator
as required for the Double Star analysis

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1. INTRODUCTION

This document is a self-contained description of the post-processing and output needed in conjunction with the IDT Preprocessing and Location Estimator, in order to preserve sufficient data for the identification and processing of double stars. Two types of output are required:

- (i) from the Location Estimator, accumulation of histogram statistics of the goodness-of-fit variable $\Delta\chi^2$ for each program star; and
- (ii) from the IDT Preprocessing, output of mean signal parameters β and information matrix for each FOV crossing of every program star.

When IDT data from the whole mission have been passed through the IDT Preprocessing and Location Estimator, the histogram statistics (i) will be used (together with *a priori* information and other data, e.g. from the SM processing and Step 2/3) to identify a limited number of program stars for which the Double Star analysis will be performed. The main input for that analysis will be the observations (ii) extracted for the relevant stars, the final attitude and instrument parameters from Step 1; the set of zero points from Step 2/3, and the (updated) Input Catalogue.

2. HISTOGRAM STATISTICS

The variable $\Delta\chi^2$ measures the statistical discrepancy between the (unconstrained) signal parameters determined by the IDT Preprocessing (the 'five-parameter fit') and the nearest set of signal parameters consistent with the single star hypothesis and current OTF calibration (the 'three-parameter fit'). The variable, which is calculated for each star and each frame, is expected to follow the chi-square distribution with 2 d.o.f., if the star is indeed single.

For double and multiple stars such that the light modulation is noticeably distorted, $\Delta\chi^2$ will tend to be larger than for single stars. To study the sample distribution of $\Delta\chi^2$ for the several hundred frames in which a given star is observed, will therefore be a fairly sensitive test of its singleness.

I have suggested elsewhere (NDAC/LO/075) that the distribution of $\Delta\chi^2$ for a given star is conveniently represented by a histogram with eight bins. The bin number ($\text{ibin} = 0, 1, 2, \dots, 7$) is computed according to the FORTRAN statement

$$\text{ibin} = \text{MIN}(7, \text{INT}(8 * \text{EXP}(-0.5 * \Delta\chi^2))) \quad (1)$$

The binning is constructed in such a way that each bin has the same probability if $\Delta\chi^2$ has the chi-square distribution with 2 d.o.f. In particular excessive counts in $\text{ibin} = 0$ is a clear indication of non-singleness. Although other representations can be discussed (e.g. with fewer bins), let us take the eight-bin histogram as baseline for the moment.

Since the maximum number of frame observations on any given star is about 4000 (mean value: ~ 1200), we can use INTEGER*2 (range 0 to 32767 not using the sign bit) for the histogram. This requires 16 bytes per star in the working catalogue, or slightly less than 2 Mb for the whole catalogue. The extra computing amounts to evaluating (1) and incrementing the histogram approximately 4 times per frame on the average.

3. MEAN SIGNAL PARAMETERS AND INFORMATION MATRIX PER FOV CROSSING

A FOV crossing is the nine or ten consecutive frames in which a given star is observable while moving across the combined FOV. Since there can never be more than 10 frames in a crossing, we shall assume that there are always 10 frames in a crossing ($k = 1, 2, \dots, 10$) and assign zero weight ($w_k = 0$) to frames in which the star was not observed.

The geometry of scanning a small object ($< 20''$) is virtually the same for all 10 frames in a crossing. From the viewpoint of double star analysis, it is therefore acceptable (indeed, preferable) to combine those frames into a single 'observation', giving the mean signal parameters and the total information matrix for the FOV crossing. By this process, the amount of output data is reduced roughly by a factor five.

However, before combining the signal parameters, we must take into account the variation of the OTF across the field and with time and colour. Moreover, the third signal parameter $\hat{\beta}_3$ (the phase of the first harmonic at frame mid-time) *cannot* be averaged at this stage of the processing (such averaging would be possible only when we have the final attitude and instrument parameters). Finally, the averaging must be weighted to take into account that the different frames carry different weight.

Input data

Consider the FOV crossing of a particular star (identification number i), consisting of the 10 frames $k = 1, 2, \dots, 10$. The crossing is identified by

- the star identification number (i);
- the mid-time of the first frame (T_1).

From the IDT Preprocessing we now have (for $k = 1, 2, \dots, 10$):

- the 5-parameter fit $\hat{\beta}_{1k}, \hat{\beta}_{2k}, \hat{\beta}_{3k}, \hat{\beta}_{4k}, \hat{\beta}_{5k}$ [units: counts/sample for the first two, radians for the third, dimensionless for the last two];
- the 5×5 information matrix $\underline{F}_k$ (symmetric; its inverse is the covariance of $\hat{\beta}_k$). $\underline{F}_k = \underline{0}$ for no observation in the frame.

Note that $\hat{\beta}_{3k}$ must refer to the frame mid-times. From the OTF Calibration we finally have:

- the calibration values $\tilde{\beta}_{4k}$ and $\tilde{\beta}_{5k}$ (corresponding to a single star).

Rectifying $\hat{\beta}_4$ and $\hat{\beta}_5$

For an 'ideal' instrument we should find $\beta_4 = R (= M_2/M_1)$ and $\beta_5 = 0$, whenever a single star is observed. The observed values $\hat{\beta}_{4k}, \hat{\beta}_{5k}$ deviate from these constants due to possible non-singleness of the star, imperfections of the optics and grid, and photon noise. The effects of optics and grid are in principle contained in the calibration values $\tilde{\beta}_{4k}, \tilde{\beta}_{5k}$, and can be

eliminated by the transformation (dropping subscript k for brevity)

$$\bar{\beta}_4 = R(\tilde{\beta}_4\hat{\beta}_4 + \tilde{\beta}_5\hat{\beta}_5)(\tilde{\beta}_4^2 + \tilde{\beta}_5^2)^{-1/2} \quad \leftarrow N\beta \quad (2a)$$

$$\bar{\beta}_5 = R(\tilde{\beta}_4\hat{\beta}_5 - \tilde{\beta}_5\hat{\beta}_4)(\tilde{\beta}_4^2 + \tilde{\beta}_5^2)^{-1/2} \quad \leftarrow N\beta \quad (2b)$$

$\hat{\beta}_1$, $\hat{\beta}_2$ and $\hat{\beta}_3$ do not require any such rectification. The transformation (2) in principle entails a slight modification of the information matrix $\underline{F}_k$. For simplicity we neglect this complication, which is probably justified provided that R is chosen close to the average real M_2/M_1 .

Calculating weights

Strictly speaking, the information matrices $\underline{F}_k$ are the correct weighting factors. The weighted mean vector $\underline{\beta}$ is thus obtained as

$$\underline{\beta} = \underline{F}^{-1}(\underline{F}_1\underline{\beta}_1 + \underline{F}_2\underline{\beta}_2 + \dots + \underline{F}_{10}\underline{\beta}_{10}) \quad (3)$$

with

$$\underline{F} = \underline{F}_1 + \underline{F}_2 + \dots + \underline{F}_{10} \quad (4)$$

indicating the weight of the average. However, we shall accept a scalar weighting system,

$$\underline{\beta} = w_1\underline{\beta}_1 + w_2\underline{\beta}_2 + \dots + w_{10}\underline{\beta}_{10} \quad (5)$$

in which w_k are simple functions of $\underline{F}_k$ (with $w_1 + w_2 + \dots + w_{10} = 1$). The proper choice of these weights is far from obvious. Provisionally, I propose to make them proportional to the third diagonal element of $\underline{F}_k$. Thus,

$$w_k = (\underline{F}_k)_{33}/(\underline{F})_{33} \quad (6)$$

The mean signal parameters

For the four parameters that can be averaged, the mean values are thus:

$$\beta_j = \sum_k w_k \hat{\beta}_{jk}, \quad j = 1, 2; \quad \beta_j = \sum_k w_k \bar{\beta}_{jk}, \quad j = 4, 5 \quad (7)$$

For the third parameter, we must retain the individual values $\hat{\beta}_{3k}$ and their weights w_k .

Output data

The output data for a single FOV crossing thus become:

- the star identification number (i);
- the mid-time of the first frame (T_1);
- the individual phases and weights for the ten frames, $\{\hat{\beta}_{3k}, w_k, k = 1 \text{ to } 10\}$;
- the mean signal parameters $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_4, \beta_5$;
- the (upper-diagonal part of the) total information matrix $\underline{F}$.

Handling of boundary crossings

At the boundary between two data batches for the IDT Preprocessing and Location Estimator, it may happen that part of a FOV crossing falls into one batch, and another part in the adjacent batch. Such a case may be regarded as two independent crossings by setting $w_k = 0$ for the missing frames (note that $\sum_k w_k = 1$ for each crossing). Partial crossings, interrupted by occultations etc, are handled in a similar manner.

Coding of output data

All output data should be coded as non-negative binary integers of length 1, 2, or 4 bytes. The rules for the tape format should be similar to those used for input to the great circle reduction (Petersen, 1986 May 6, issue 1). A provisional format for the FOV crossing record is given in the next section. Considerations for the scaling and transformation of output data are given below.

Flux range. The minimum flux is zero or (if a positive estimate is required) corresponds to the dark current of the IDT: nominally 18.5 Hz but could be lower (?). Maximum flux corresponds to $B = -1.5$ (Sirius), or 43 MHz (BOL). Thus the range of $E(N_\ell)$ is 10^{-2} to $4 \cdot 10^4$ counts/sample. This is also the range for β_1 and β_2 .

Number of samples. The number of samples in a crossing ranges from 8 to approximately 9 times 2560 $\approx$ 23000.

Diagonal elements of F. With

$$E(N_{\ell}) = I_{\ell} = \beta_1 + \beta_2 [\cos(H_{\ell} + \beta_3) + \beta_4 \cos 2(H_{\ell} + \beta_3) + \beta_5 \sin 2(H_{\ell} + \beta_3)] \quad (8)$$

the diagonal elements of $\underline{F}$ will be

$$F_{jj} = \sum_{k,\ell} \frac{1}{I_{\ell}} \left(\frac{\partial I_{\ell}}{\partial \beta_j} \right)^2 \quad (9)$$

Using that

$$\begin{aligned} |\partial I_{\ell} / \partial \beta_1| &= 1, & |\partial I_{\ell} / \partial \beta_2| &\leq 1 + R < 1.5, & |\partial I_{\ell} / \partial \beta_3| &\leq (1 + 2R)\beta_2 < 2\beta_1, \\ |\partial I_{\ell} / \partial \beta_4| &\leq \beta_2 < \beta_1, & |\partial I_{\ell} / \partial \beta_5| &\leq \beta_2 < \beta_1 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

and the ranges above for β_1 and the number of samples, we find:

$$\begin{array}{rclcl} 2 \cdot 10^{-4} & < & F_{11} & < & 3 \cdot 10^6 & \text{(typical } \sim 2000) \\ 1 \cdot 10^{-4} & < & F_{22} & < & 6 \cdot 10^6 & \text{(typical } \sim 1000) \\ 0.3 & < & F_{33} & < & 4 \cdot 10^9 & \text{(typical } \sim 4000) \\ 0.1 & < & F_{44} & < & 10^9 & \text{(typical } \sim 4000) \\ 0.1 & < & F_{55} & < & 10^9 & \text{(typical } \sim 4000) \end{array}$$

(The typical numbers are for 5500 samples of a star of magnitude $B_r = 9$.)
 F_{33} , F_{44} and F_{55} may actually become zero if there is no light modulation ($\beta_2 = 0$).

Off-diagonal elements of F

Thanks to the non-negative definiteness of $\underline{F}$, the normalized off-diagonal elements

$$\phi_{ij} = F_{ij} / (F_{ii} F_{jj})^{1/2} \quad (11)$$

will satisfy

$$|\phi_{ij}| \leq 1 \quad (12)$$

This suggests that the off-diagonal elements are best stored in their normalized form. If square-root compression is used for the diagonal elements, then the normalizations (11) need not involve additional square root extractions.

Proposed coding

Table 1 summarizes the suggested codings and permitted ranges for the output data (except star number and frame mid-time).

Table 1. Proposed coding and permitted ranges for output data

datum	transformation	bytes	permitted range of datum
$\hat{\beta}_{3k}$	$\text{nint}(1e4*\hat{\beta}_{3k}/2\pi)$	2	0 to 2π
w_k	$\text{nint}(1e4*w_k)$	2	0 to 1
β_1	$\text{nint}[(1e4*\beta_1)^{\frac{1}{2}}]$	2	0 to $1.07 \cdot 10^5$
β_2	$\text{nint}[(1e4*\beta_2)^{\frac{1}{2}}]$	2	0 to $1.07 \cdot 10^5$
β_4	$\text{nint}[1e4*(1+\beta_4)]$	2	-1 to 1
β_5	$\text{nint}[1e4*(1+\beta_5)]$	2	-1 to 1
F_{11}	$\text{nint}[(1e10*F_{11})^{\frac{1}{2}}]$	4	0 to $4.61 \cdot 10^8$
F_{22}	$\text{nint}[(1e10*F_{22})^{\frac{1}{2}}]$	4	0 to $4.61 \cdot 10^8$
F_{33}	$\text{nint}[(1e8*F_{33})^{\frac{1}{2}}]$	4	0 to $4.61 \cdot 10^{10}$
F_{44}	$\text{nint}[(1e8*F_{44})^{\frac{1}{2}}]$	4	0 to $4.61 \cdot 10^{10}$
F_{55}	$\text{nint}[(1e8*F_{55})^{\frac{1}{2}}]$	4	0 to $4.61 \cdot 10^{10}$
ϕ_{ij}	$\text{nint}[1e4*(1+\phi_{ij})]$	2	-1 to 1

Notes:

1. The largest non-negative binary integer is -
with 2 bytes: $2^{15}-1 = 32767$
with 4 bytes: $2^{31}-1 = 2,147,483,647$
2. Although $\sum_k w_k = 1$, the sum of the coded weights, $\sum_k \text{nint}(1e4*w_k)$, may be anything from 9996 to 10004. This problem is taken care of at the receiving end (Double Star analysis) by re-normalizing the weights after conversion to real numbers.

Data amounts

Each FOV crossing requires 100 bytes with the proposed coding (Section 4). The total number of crossings is obtained by dividing the number of frame observations with 9, i.e. for 2.5 years and 115,000 stars:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{number of FOV crossings} &= \frac{(\text{number of frames}) \times (\text{observations per frame})}{9} \\ &\approx \frac{3.7 \cdot 10^7 \times 4.5}{9} \\ &\approx 2 \cdot 10^7 \end{aligned}$$

The total size of the FOV crossing records is thus about 2000 Mbytes, or ≈ 50 tapes (1600 bpi). If 6250 bpi is used, some 15 tapes are required.

4. TAPE FORMAT FOR FOV CROSSING RECORDS

The specifications for input to the great circle reduction program system (Petersen, 1986 May 6) apply as far as possible. Thus, files are organized in one or more blocks of 8192 bytes. The first block in a file is a file header block, containing a file label record and a FOV crossing file header record. These specify the type of data on the file, the time interval covered by the data, and the length and number of data records contained in the following blocks. The second and following blocks are data blocks, containing a block header record and a number of FOV crossing records. The descriptions of the different records below follow the conventions in Petersen's document.

File header block

File label record

Word	Off	Len	Description
1	0	4	'NDAC' = general identifier
2	4	4	'FOVC' = data type identifier (FOV crossings)
3	8	8	tape identifier (max 8 characters)
5	16	4	processing time in seconds since 1988.0
6	20	4	= 3 version number of file label format
7	24	4	= 8 number of words in the file label
8	28	4	= 2048 number of words in a block (max)

FOV crossing file header record

Word	Off	Len	Description
9	32	4	= 8 number of words in this header record
10	36	4	= 1 version number of FOV crossing format
11	40	4	= 25 number of words in a FOV crossing record
12	44	4	time of the first frame used in s since 1988.0
13	48	4	time of the last frame used in s since 1988.0
14	52	4	FOV crossing file number
15	56	4	= 0 (not used - spare)
16	60	4	number of FOV crossing records in the file

Data blocksBlock header record

Word	Off	Len	Description
1	0	4	= 2 number of words in this block header record
2	4	4	number of FOV crossing records in this block

FOV crossing record

Name	Off	Len	Description
IDSTAR	0	4	star identification number
FMTIME	4	4	mid-time of the first frame of the FOV crossing in seconds since 1988.0
	8	4	micro-seconds part of the frame mid-time
WEIGHT(1)	12	2	weight of the first frame (w_1) stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*w_1)$
BETA3(1)	14	2	modulation phase of the first frame ($\hat{\beta}_{3,1}$) stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*\hat{\beta}_{3,1}/2\pi)$
⋮	⋮	⋮	⋮
WEIGHT(10)	48	2	weight of the 10th frame (w_{10}) stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*w_{10})$
BETA3(10)	50	2	modulation phase of the 10th frame ($\hat{\beta}_{3,10}$) stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*\hat{\beta}_{3,10}/2\pi)$
BETA1	52	2	mean signal parameter β_1 stored as $\text{nint}(\text{sqrt}(1e4*\beta_1))$
BETA2	54	2	mean signal parameter β_2 stored as $\text{nint}(\text{sqrt}(1e4*\beta_2))$
BETA4	56	2	mean signal parameter β_4 stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*(1.+\beta_4))$
BETA5	58	2	mean signal parameter β_5 stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*(1.+\beta_5))$
FINF(1,1)	60	4	Fisher information matrix element F_{11} stored as $\text{nint}(1e5*\text{sqrt}(F_{11}))$
FINF(2,2)	64	4	matrix element F_{22} stored as $\text{nint}(1e5*\text{sqrt}(F_{22}))$
FINF(3,3)	68	4	matrix element F_{33} stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*\text{sqrt}(F_{33}))$
FINF(4,4)	72	4	matrix element F_{44} stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*\text{sqrt}(F_{44}))$
FINF(5,5)	76	4	matrix element F_{55} stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*\text{sqrt}(F_{55}))$

(continued)

FOV crossing record (continued)

Name	Off	Len	Description
FINF(1,2)	80	2	F_{12} stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*(1.+F_{12}/\text{sqrt}(F_{11}*F_{12})))$
FINF(1,3)	82	2	F_{13} stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*(1.+F_{13}/\text{sqrt}(F_{11}*F_{12})))$
FINF(2,3)	84	2	F_{23} stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*(1.+F_{23}/\text{sqrt}(F_{22}*F_{33})))$
FINF(1,4)	86	2	F_{14} stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*(1.+F_{14}/\text{sqrt}(F_{11}*F_{44})))$
FINF(2,4)	88	2	F_{24} stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*(1.+F_{24}/\text{sqrt}(F_{22}*F_{44})))$
FINF(3,4)	90	2	F_{34} stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*(1.+F_{34}/\text{sqrt}(F_{33}*F_{44})))$
FINF(1,5)	92	2	F_{15} stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*(1.+F_{15}/\text{sqrt}(F_{11}*F_{55})))$
FINF(2,5)	94	2	F_{25} stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*(1.+F_{25}/\text{sqrt}(F_{22}*F_{55})))$
FINF(3,5)	96	2	F_{35} stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*(1.+F_{35}/\text{sqrt}(F_{33}*F_{55})))$
FINF(4,5)	98	2	F_{45} stored as $\text{nint}(1e4*(1.+F_{45}/\text{sqrt}(F_{44}*F_{55})))$